

SPECIAL CONSIDERATIONS IN TESTING ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS
REINFORCED WITH KEVLAR* ARAMID FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Special techniques for preparation and testing of composite specimens reinforced with "Kevlar" aramid fibers are discussed, along with comparative data illustrating the effects of certain test variables on coupon tensile, compression, shear, and flexure.

INTRODUCTION

Among the many challenges facing the composites community today is the development and standardization of reliable test methods for basic mechanical properties of composites and their constituents. Testing of advanced composite materials is complicated by the high strength and stiffness, low strain to failure, inhomogeneity and anisotropy of the materials, to cite only the obvious. In addition, techniques which are appropriate for one particular composite form may not be applicable to others of the many possible combinations of reinforcement and matrix.

Among the fibers presently used in advanced composites, the "Kevlar" aramid fibers present some unique challenges in specimen design, preparation, and testing. We would like to share some of the learnings from over a decade of experience with these materials, reviewing several important test methods and the adaptations which have been required for "Kevlar". Because this must necessarily be a superficial treatment, those interested in further details are invited to contact the authors.

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SPECIMEN PREPARATION

A common problem in preparing specimens from composites containing "Kevlar" aramid fibers is difficulty in machining clean, fuzz free edges. Tooling and techniques for machining have been discussed in detail elsewhere [1]. For straight sided coupons we usually rough cut the specimens about 1/16" oversize using a band saw or table saw, then wet grind to final size using a diamond faced wheel. (Only water is used as a lubricant).

Unless otherwise noted, data presented are on unidirectional prepreg tapes of "Kevlar" 49/MXM 7714 (Fiberite) and AS-4 carbon/F-155 (Hexcel), both 250° rubber toughened epoxies, cured per the manufacturer's recommendations.

UNIDIRECTIONAL COUPON TENSILE

A straight-sided coupon with bonded tabs or doublers (ASTM D-3039) is recommend for 0° specimens. Our standard specimen and tabbing procedure are shown in Figure 1. Tabs are at least 2" long to help prevent debonding.

FIGURE 1. Tensile coupon and tabbing procedure.

It is common practice with carbon fiber composites to apply doubler material to a plate from which individual specimens are then cut with a diamond saw. Because of the high toughness of the "Kevlar" fiber this approach is not recommended--it tends to induce excessive edge damage. Instead, specimens are precut to size and tabbed individually. Key points are:

- Specimen ends are abraded only where they will be covered by the tabs.
- Tabs are precision machined to be 1/16" wider than the specimens to be tabbed. This gives a margin of error to compensate for small tab misalignments and variations in specimen width.

- o The tabbing jig facilitates alignment of the tabs and applies pressure to the specimens during adhesive cure. After the tabs and specimens are aligned they are pressed down against the reference surface before the jig is fully tightened.

In a good specimen the tabs cover the full width of the specimen, are well aligned with the specimen edges and each other, no adhesive extends beyond the tab, the specimen edges are clean and delamination free, and the fiber direction is well aligned with the load axis. This last has proved to be a very significant source of error in testing of composites with "Kevlar" aramid fibers. The effect of fiber misalignment on apparent fiber stress at failure in carefully prepared filament wound panels is shown in Figure 2. The unidirectional panels were deliberately cracked down the center and the fracture line was used as the 0° reference from which to measure the cutting angle. Misalignment of the order of $.5^\circ$ to 1° causes a drop in apparent strength of as much as 20%.

FIGURE 2. Effect of fiber misalignment on apparent stress at failure in tensile coupons ("Kevlar" 49 aramid in EPON 828/NMA/BDMA). Each point is the average of at least 3 determinations. Error bars are ± 2 standard deviations.

Figure 2 also shows the range of some typical commercial unitape prepreps containing "Kevlar". These materials deliver considerably lower strength than the same fiber in our filament wound panels. We believe this is due to fiber misalignment from catenary (slack fibers) in the tows used to make the prepreg, poor tension control leading to waviness in the tow during prepregging, and misalignment between plies during lay-up.

Figure 3 illustrates how severe the problem can be. The carbon tracer yarn in Item A makes local lateral excursions of as much as ± 0.04 " from the axis, as well as having longer wavelength deviations from linearity.

FIGURE 3. Typical tensile specimens from two commercial prepregs. TOP: Item A, note severe fiber misalignment. BOTTOM: Item B.

Item A has both lower fiber stress at failure and lower modulus than Item B. (Both are chemically similar 250°F cure epoxy resin systems.) Neither material, however, approaches the strength or modulus of specimens from the filament wound panels.

FIGURE 4: Typical failure modes for unidirectional tensile coupons. TOP: Item A, local failure at fiber kinks. CENTER: Item B, longitudinal splitting. BOTTOM: Filament wound composite, global failure.

The failures in Item A tend to be localized at the more serious kinks, Figure 4. Specimens from Item B fail more globally, with multiple longitudinal splits, while the filament wound specimens show even more massive splitting (broom straw effect). We consider global failure by spitting to be the desired failure mode. The highest tensile strengths are associated

with type of behavior. Poor failures are usually one of two types--localized failure as in Item A above, or bond line failure under the tabs.

Total bond line failure is readily recognizable; partial debonding, however, is a common, undesirable failure mode which is not widely recognized. Typically the first failure event in 0° coupons is a longitudinal crack. Frequently the shock associated with this crack results in debonding of a segment of the specimen which then pulls out relatively undamaged. The remaining segment may then fail, or the test may be terminated because of the load drop which occurs at debonding. The result is low apparent breaking strength. This failure mode can be detected by examining the tabbed ends for evidence of pull out.

Longer tabs and better surface preparation for bonding--removal of all release agents is critical--may alleviate the debonding problem. However, an additional factor which is extremely important is the lateral pressure applied by the grips during testing. For specimens with over 2000 lb breaking load we recommend the use of hydraulically actuated grips which give positive, controlled pressure--self-tightening, mechanical wedge action grips do not apply sufficient pressure, nor is the pressure constant. Pressure of 800-1200 psi on the tabs gives good results for our standard specimen. At lower pressure the partial debond failure mode occurs and the results are low. At higher pressure the specimens are crushed when the grips are closed.

Tab material itself does not appear to have a large effect on the apparent tensile properties of composites with "Kevlar" (Table 1). Our standard material is a 1/8" glass fabric/epoxy circuit board stock (MIL-P-18177, Type GEE) which is readily available and easy to machine. For room temperature testing an inexpensive hardware-store variety 2 part epoxy has proved to be adequate.

TABLE 1
TENSILE STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES (kpsi)
Average of 10 (% C.V.)

Tab Type Adhesive	Standard Clear#	Aluminum Clear	Aluminum Filled*	Plate Tabbed
"Kevlar" 49 aramid/ MXM 7714	182.3 (4.4)	197.5 (3.7)	193.4 (6.9)	171.1 (6.2)
AS-4 Carbon/ F-155	201.8 (3.6)		218.5 (4.2)	216.7 (4.8)
#Epoxy Patch Hysol Div., Dexter Corp. Olean, NY 14760 USA	0151 Clear	*Special F Epoxy, Stock No. 19770 Devcon Corp. Danvers, MA 10923 USA		

Slightly higher strength was achieved with aluminum tabs using the clear adhesive, but the differences are small except for the plate tabbed item which shows the effect of cutting specimens to size after tabbing.

For strain instrumentation we make extensive use of the Dual Sensor Strain Transducer (DSST, produced by Measurements Technology, Inc., Roswell, GA. 30075). This is a clip-on device with an effective gage length of 1". It can measure two longitudinal strains simultaneously, giving the equivalent of a back-to-back gage installation. Because of concerns about the accuracy of this device as compared with bonded strain gages, we ran tests with the transducer mounted over long length (.75") bonded strain gages. Results from the DSST have consistently been equivalent to strain gage results within experimental error. Because of the good agreement in these comparisons we have adopted the transducer for routine uniaxial tensile tests, resulting in considerably savings in time and money.

COMPRESSION

Compression testing of unidirectional coupons is one of the most hotly debated issues in composites testing. There are several types of fixtures used for compression testing [2]. Of these we have experience with "Celanese", "IITRI" (both ASTM D 3410), and "modified ASTM D 695". The Celanese fixture has a cylindrical geometry and IITRI is rectangular, but the principle is the same.

There is increasing interest in the "modified ASTM" but the referenced method is intended only for unreinforced plastics and its applicability to advanced composites has not been established. We recently ran two different types of specimens in this fixture (Figure 5) for comparison with results from other fixtures.

FIGURE 5. Two advanced composite specimens for the "ASTM D-695" fixture, reduced section and tabbed.

The reduced section specimen proved to be unsuitable for "Kevlar" because of the difficulty in machining a clean section. This is reflected in lower strength and higher scatter (Table 2). Carbon also did not perform as well in the reduced section specimen, probably because of stress concentrations at the notch roots.

TABLE 2
 COMPRESSION STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES
MEASURED IN "ASTM" TYPE FIXTURE (kpsi)
 Average of at least 5 determinations (%C.V.)

Specimen Type	Reduced	Tabbed
"Kevlar" 49 aramid/ MXM 7714	37.3 (7.7)	41.3 (5.5)
AS-4 Carbon/ F-155	147.8 (10.9)	176.7 (8.9)

The tabbed specimens were prepared by sandwiching a plate of the material to be tested between two plates of tab material with film adhesive which was cured in an autoclave (vacuum bag). Specimens were then cut to the proper width with a cut off saw and, as a final step, the tab material was machined away in the gage section using an end mill. (Because the specimen is fully backed by the tab material during cutting it is possible to use a cut off saw on the panel with "Kevlar" without introducing edge damage.) Strengths of these specimens are comparable to those measured with other support fixtures.

We attempted to measure modulus both by clipping a DSST to the edges of the specimen and by bonding strain gages into the gage section. The DSST gave values for modulus 1.5 to 2X the expected value, probably because of the support provided by the fixture. The strain gage technique proved unworkable because of the very small gage section. Consequently we do not recommend this fixture for modulus measurements.

Our current preference for compression testing is the IITRI geometry with a 1/2" wide coupon specimen. The reasons for preferring this fixture over the Celanese geometry are:

- The Celanese fixture requires precisely controlled thickness for specimen plus tabs. If thickness is too great the collets "rock" inside the bolster; if too small, the specimen slips. IITRI is not subject to this problem.
- The wider IITRI specimen is more representative of structural response.
- Tabs for Celanese specimens must be exactly the same width as the specimen while IITRI specimens can use the 1/16" oversize tabs. Because we normally tab specimens with "Kevlar" after cutting, the over width tabs are an advantage.

Specimen preparation and tabbing for compression is done the same as for tension, that is, the specimens are precut and wet ground to size, then tabs are bonded on in a tabbing fixture. We use square cut tabs (no taper) from the same stock as the tabs for tensile specimens. For either Celanese or IITRI a DSST with a gage length of 0.3" is used for strain measurement eliminating the need for strain gages.

SHEAR

Like compression testing, the determination of in-plane shear properties is highly controversial [3]. Among the candidates are the 10° off axis tensile coupon, the +45° tensile coupon (ASTM D 3518) and, more recently, the Iosipescu geometry. Of these we favor the +45° tensile coupon.

The 10° off axis coupon specimen is based on the the anticipated state of stress in a carbon fiber composite [4], and it is not apparent that 10° is the correct angle for use with "Kevlar" fiber which has different anisotropy of strength and stiffness.

The Iosipescus fixture has recently become fashionable for both in-plane and interlaminar shear testing. There are still serious unresolved questions about the true state of stress in the specimen gage section and it seems likely that each fiber type may require a different notch angle. Aside from this, there is the matter of machining such a complex shape without excessive edge damage. Our first attempts on composites reinforced with "Kevlar" using traditional cutting tools were not successful. Since then we have had some success with laser cutting, and we anticipate that abrasive waterjet cutting may ultimately solve this problem.

Interlaminar shear by the short beam method (ASTM D 2344) is one of the most commonly measured, and most commonly maligned, properties of composite materials. Whatever its merits, however, SBS is likely to remain a staple of our testing menus for years to come and needs to be addressed. We have looked at two parameters, span to depth ratio and support radii (Table 3).

TABLE 3
SHORT BEAM SHEAR STRENGTH (kpsi)
Average of at least 5 determinations (% C.V.)

Span to Depth Ratio	4/1	4/1	5/1
Support Radii	1/16"	1/8"	1/16"
"Kevlar" 49 aramid/ MXM 7714	9.24 (2.7)	9.08 (2.1)	8.91 (5.8)
AS-4 Carbon/ F-155	13.9 (1.8)		12.5 (0.7)

For both "Kevlar" and carbon the highest and most consistent values were obtained with the 4 to 1 span to depth ratio and 1/16" radius supports.

The failure mode of composites with "Kevlar" in this test is clearly not interlaminar shear. It begins as yielding under the loading nose, then proceeds as shear bands propagating from this point to the lower edge at about a 45° angle. The effect of span to depth has recently been discussed in the literature [5].

FLEXURE

Another type of test which is widely performed, although the results tend to be viewed with suspicion, is flexure (ASTM D 790). The key variable in flexure of composites with "Kevlar" is the span to depth ratio [6]. Because of shear displacement, the apparent modulus measured may be significantly different from the tensile modulus if the span to depth ratio is too small (Figure 6).

FIGURE 6. Apparent flexural modulus of composites as a function of span to depth ratio and loading configuration.

On the other hand, if the span to depth ratio is too large, lateral forces, which are neglected in the standard equations, become significant and the apparent strength decreases (Figure 7).

FIGURE 7. Apparent flexural strength as a function of span to depth ratio and loading configuration.

Carbon composites show the former effect, but not the latter. Span to depth ratio of 60/1 is recommended for modulus determinations with "Kevlar" and 16/1 for strength.

CONCLUSIONS

Because of the unique properties of the "Kevlar" aramid fibers it is necessary to make some changes and adaptations in the standard test methods. These are partly in response to the greater difficulty in machining clean specimens, and partly a result of fiber properties such as anisotropy in strength and stiffness which differ from one reinforcement to another.

REFERENCES

1. "A Guide to Cutting and Machining Materials Containing "Kevlar" Aramid Fibers", Preliminary Information Bulletin Number 446, DuPont Co., Wilmington, DE, 1983.
2. Hofer, K. E. and Rao, P. N., "A New Static Compression Fixture for Advanced Composite Materials", J. Testing and Evaluation, 1977, Vol. 5, No. 4, pp. 278-283.
3. Lee, S. and Munro, M., "Evaluation of In-Plane Shear Test Methods for Advanced Composite Materials by the Decision Analysis Technique", Composites, Vol. 17, No. 1, 1986, pp 13-22.
4. Chamis, C. C. and Sinclair, J. H., "10° Off Axis Tensile Test for Intra-laminar Shear Characterization of Fiber Composites, NASA Tech Note D-8215, Lewis Research Center, Cleveland, OH, April 1976.
5. Fischer, S., Rosensaft, M., and Marom, G., "Dependence of the Inter-laminar Shear Strength on the Loading Span-to-Depth Ratio in Aramid Fibre-Reinforced Beams", Comp. Sci. & Tech., Vol. 25, 1986, pp. 69-73.
6. Zweben, C., Wardle, M. W., and Smith, W. S., "Test Methods for Fiber Tensile Strength, Composite Flex Modulus, and Properties of Fabric Reinforced Laminates", STP 674, ASTM, Philadelphia, 1979, pp. 228-262.